

THE BAD, THE UGLY, THE MISERABLE IN EVIDENCE-BASED DENTISTRY

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**Note: This draft was initially sent as an entry for an essay writing competition organized by a prominent scholarly body.*

It has been nearly three decades into the 21st century. Moreover, almost 35 years after its introduction to the world, the fact that the topic of evidence-based dentistry still finds itself as a theme in essay-writing competition speaks volumes about the sombreness of pedodontists in a domain that is central to modern healthcare.

The word 'practice' is presumably associated with clinical skills that a pediatric dentist picks up as they hone their abilities over the years. However, since evidence-based healthcare gained momentum globally, the term practice has expanded its scope to include experimental and descriptive research, medicolegal systems, and academic integrity. It has also led to scholarly publishing emerging as a thriving industry, which has become a fulcrum for clinical practice.

The glaring ignorance of inculcating evidence-based dentistry as a mandatory subject in the dental curriculum in several countries has resulted in a research inaptitude. In the paragraph to follow, I shall go on a rant. This rant shall address both practices and challenges, as stipulated by several bodies that govern the clinico-academic systems. In return, my words too demand the attention of the assessor's pupils (both your eyes and your students) with a hope that by the time you reach the end of this document, you garner enough courage to call a spade, a spade.

THE CHALLENGING PRACTICES

Nobody better than pediatric dentists understands the importance of age as a measure of time. By the time they enter the early 20s, they are academically tagged as 'Masters' by the governing bodies. In this journey, the unaware are triggered by the unethical to publish their 'evidence-based research' in questionable journals. However, cases of intentional academic breach where the ones aware lure the unaware to engage in such bogus practices are not uncommon.

An academic culture rich in illegitimate activities is solely due to the mindset that has been prevalent over the years. A young scholar faces rejection once or twice, reaches the end of their patience, and gives up all hopes of pursuing a career in academia (if ever there was one). They may or may not address the concerns associated with rejection. Should a 'high volume' or 'a great influx of articles' or 'beyond the scope' be the basis of rejection, then it is clearly due to a research inaptitude. Such incompetencies have arisen from the lack of evidence-based healthcare in the curricula, the absence of journal evaluation as a subject, inadequate critical evaluation skills for scientific manuscripts, and the failure to have an introductory chapter on the requirements of scientific writing.

Research misconduct is fascinating. I say this because it has a domino effect. If one falls, a cascade ensues. No individual can commit only one research misconduct. If a manuscript is forcing a significant p-value, not only does it add to p-value hacking, but also to data dredging. If the author forces a citation of their own or their supervisor's work, not only are they indulging in citation manipulation, but also in a lack of accountability. For example, at the end of this sentence, I will provide in-text citations to four of my published works which may or may not be related to the preceding sentences and that is how the h-index can be manipulated despite there being a major redundancy flaw that sees a sentence as long as this one pass through the copyeditors and find itself published in what maybe an essay writing competition, a white paper, a grey paper, papers of colors of all sorts, and god forbid, scholarly manuscripts that are yelling and pleading to be rejected, retracted, and revoked given the dreadful nature of the idioms and phrases in this apologetic statement.(1–4)

Failure to report the trial registry or ethics committee number of a study done on human subjects is an ethical breach credited to the triad of scholarly publishing workforce - authors, reviewers, and publishers. It is one of the many facets of scientific integrity violations credited to the fortress called scholarly publishing. The Clinical Trials Registry of India made it a mandate in 2018 to register research conducted on human subjects prospectively. This law is unanimously supported by the Committee on Publication Ethics, the International Committee of Medical

Journal Editors, and the World Association of Medical Editors. These are the same three bodies that journals quote while stating that they follow their guidelines, despite blatantly ignoring mention of trial registry numbers.

Suppose a young scholar is in awe of a journal's unsolicited mail that claims to have a reputed index and has a fast acceptance rate. In that case, they are falling prey to not only compromised peer-review, but also the highly probable scenario of their work being removed from the journal website altogether due to the absence of an archival source and the inability to assign a persistent object identifier.

At the helm of all research misconducts are paper mills. The sale of authorship slots in purchased manuscripts of journals indexed through a compromise has been the reason why South Asians have lacked the proactiveness to know about the basics of research in the first place. The same author will feature in multiple manuscripts in the same issue, or the same manuscript will be published in another journal with rotating authorship, or a group of authors may have a shady contractual association with specific journals. Courtesy of WhatsApp, the dark deeds of the administrators of some groups will continue to ensure that research stays within the peripheries of an essay writing competition.

Two wrongs can never make a right. As professionals, we have miserably failed to terminate illegal practices. As pedodontists, our combined research quotient is arguably lower than most. In our pursuit of academic promotions, we have resorted to steps that have tainted our global representation. And at the cost of what? Simple, basic education on evidence-based dentistry. Academicians have failed at their fundamental role of educating the next generation, and clinicians have successfully shied away from their responsibility by announcing a demarcation between clinicians and academicians.

It is safe to say that these challenges have found a shelf-life with the advent of artificial intelligence. If I am submitting this work, are the evaluators aware of the tools to detect AI-generated content? What if this were a manuscript where the text is full of hallucinations, and a clinical topic has passed the review stages with lapses in reasoning? Individuals seeking to enhance their academic credentials for academic promotions and gains are now aware of tools that can humanize AI-generated texts. There is nothing wrong with machine learning systems. The problem is that the ones who made those systems do not want to learn their subject in the first place. There can be no better example of this than the ongoing academic misconduct involving AI-generated peer reviews. The peer reviewers fail to proofread the generated text and submit it with command prompts embedded within the review. If this is the state of peer reviews, then I do not feel the need to explain how authors exploit machine learning for manuscript writing.

THE OPPORTUNITIES THAT SLIP AWAY

Figure 1 The inverted pyramid of academic obstacles

Now that we know (or we already knew) the practices, let's review the deeds that disallow the creation of opportunities. Imagine this as an inverted pyramid where the most basic challenges to surmount are language and advice from peers (Figure 1). To struggle with language is common, as the global communication medium (English) is not native to us. At the same time, one must not forget that it is after five years of undergraduate studies, and late into the first year of postgraduate studies, when a student first attempts to write a scientific manuscript. Even if the schooling was in a vernacular medium, these six years are enough to develop basic writing skills. The basics include writing a grammatically correct sentence in a language that the student has been reading since they were in school.

An added dimension that scientific writing demands is that every sentence must convey a meaning. Unlike academic writing (the one which students resort to in exams), which allows a leeway for the writer to drift and make bridges across two ideas, the flow in scientific writing needs a neat camouflage where the reader does not realize how they have traversed between two notions.

Despite submission guidelines specifically stating to follow the reporting standards as recommended by the Equator Network (EN), authors often fail to do so. For those who lack confidence in drafting a manuscript, nothing can help them boost their morale more than following the EN guidelines. It acts like a stepwise checklist, following which the first draft appears fluid enough, requiring minimal corrections in terms of syntax and semantics. The

frontier of scientific writing is a tall ask, but achievable with guidance from seniors or supervisors. Here we meet our second challenge, advice from peers.

In biomedical sciences, students learn a lot from their seniors. In pediatric dentistry, many dedicate their clinical skills which they learned to their seniors. Unfortunately, the translation of this practice for imparting guidance on research has not made its mark. Unless universities make evidence-based dentistry a compulsory exam-going subject, it is hard to imagine a healthy academic environment wherein the seniors guide their juniors in this field. Moreover, having known how a predatory publication can help them tick the criteria for securing a master's degree, no student will ever take the prospect of research with the seriousness it deserves.

The next big task to overcome is the inflexibility and the rigidity of certain academicians in favor of research. To them, I ask, what makes you an academician? Teaching & counselling students? Taking lectures in air-conditioned halls? Ensuring to keep their college management elated? Going to conferences without participation to earn tours and travel brownie points? None of these are 'exceptions' that characterize you as an academician. To these you were dutifully bound the very day of your induction as a tutor or lecturer. Whether you accept it or not, it is the R-word that will help you earn the title of an academician.

This same group of so-called academics is also hell-bent on avoiding staying updated with the different modes of knowledge acquisition. It is a known fact that textbooks of international authors are often an expensive purchase. At the same time, most of them are available in electronic format, which can be downloaded or bought. But there is an old-fashioned group that will always live in the nostalgic belief that clings to 'I can't read if there is not an actual book (hard copy) in my hand' and has thus indefinitely decided to stay outdated. As an ardent novel reader, I, too, belonged to this group once. But I realized reading E-books is the way ahead, especially in the field of research, where the definition of 'recent' changes every single day.

From e-books, it is imperative to move on to our beloved manuscripts. The penultimate tier, thus, is the habit of reading and critically evaluating scholarly articles. At the institutional level, the rules of the journal club vary. At times, the student is asked only to refer to selected standard publication houses. They are asked to refer only to 'international' journals (where neither the mentors nor the mentees know what makes a journal international), or at times, there is no bar on the journal or article selection process. In the latter, the most dangerous scenario can be one where neither the teachers nor the students are aware of what constitutes a fraudulent publication.

The best journals, in my opinion, are the ones that follow a gold open access model only (no hybrid systems). These are the ones that will charge a minimum of 15,000 INR for publication, will promise a peer review, and are likely to publish the article in under three months. Two of the three traits I mentioned are solid identifiers of questionable publication houses. By evaluating such publications, students can pose several questions to the published works, and their guides can help them identify areas for improvement in the manuscript (with the first teaching being journal selection).

At the helm of our problems are the auditors or the inspectors. Periodically, these inspectors visit institutes recognized by the apex governing body. One of their tasks includes a scrutiny of the publications of each faculty member. The count of publications is pivotal in deciding whether the individual deserves to hold on to or be promoted based on a points system that was last revised two Olympics ago. Given the spread of research inaptitude in the country and the bulk that we contribute to in predatory publishing, it is natural to ponder, who audits the auditors? Do they have an assessment system for the inspectors' knowledge on journal/publication evaluation? And if farce publications are the norm, why even bother having an inspection in the first place?

Some tales have been heard, rumoured, believed, and talked about. In our interest, we keep mum. The silence is deafening, as are our research prospects.

REFERENCES

1. Shukla B, Panda A. Development, Reliability, and Validity of the DIP-DIP Scale for Quick Diagnosis of Predatory Journals. *J Sch Publ.* 2025 Jul 1;56(3):650–61. DOI: 10.3138/jsp-2024-0059
2. Shukla B, Panda A. The Deuce List - A Tool to Evaluate Journals and A Mini-review on Predatory Publishing. *Int J Recent Surg Med Sci.* 2025 May 5;11:e006. DOI: 10.25259/ijrsms_11_2025
3. Shukla B, Panda A. The G.R.A.P.E. Checklist for Students of Healthcare to Finetune and Safeguard their Scholarly Manuscripts. *Kathmandu Univ Med J KUMJ.* 2025;22(88):123–6. PMID: 40464248
4. Shukla B, Panda A. A quality exploration of machine learning's ability to predict predatory dental publications. *COLLNET J Scientometr Inf Manag.* 2025;19(1):59–70. DOI: 10.47974/CJSIM-2024-11002